

Veterinary Science Reports

Feet deformity in Eastern Cattle Egret (*Ardea coromanda*)

Hebbal Rajendra Abhilash^{1*}

¹Sri Hari, Mukthidhama road, Hootagalli, Mysore – 570018, Karnataka, India

²St. Mary's road, N.R. Mohalla, Mysore – 570007, Karnataka, India

*Corresponding author: abhilash2787@gmail.com

ARTICLE HISTORY

ABSTRACT

Received: 17.04.2026
Revised: 13.05.2026
Accepted: 25.05.2026
Published online: 31.05.2026

An adult Eastern cattle egret (*Ardea coromanda*) with limb deformity was observed during flight at Huyilalu Lake, Mysore, Karnataka, India, on 7th February 2026. On close photographic observation, the bird exhibited asymmetric limbs with fused digits, and both feet hung loosely during flight, indicating impaired locomotion and reduced muscular control. Such deformities can affect balance, foraging efficiency, predator avoidance, and survival. Documentation of such abnormalities in free-ranging birds contributes to veterinary literature and avian health surveillance.

Key words: Eastern cattle egret; foot deformity; wildlife health

I. INTRODUCTION

The Eastern cattle egret (*Ardea coromanda*) is a medium-sized heron widely distributed across southern and eastern Asia and Australasia (Krebs 1994; Rasmussen & Anderton, 2005). Taxonomically,

this species was first classified under the genus *Bubulcus* (*Bubulcus ibis*) but has since been reassigned to the genus *Ardea* based on molecular analyses (Hruska et al., 2023). This species exhibits strong ecological plasticity and is commonly associated with grazing livestock and agricultural landscapes and has

also been observed to forage alongside farm tractors and mowing machinery, where it feeds opportunistically on insects, arachnids, and small vertebrates disturbed by anthropogenic or animal activity (Veeramani & Agalya, 2023; Telfair et al., 2024). The egret's close association with human-modified habitats makes it particularly relevant as a bio-indicator species for environmental health assessment (Lesch et al., 2024). Limb deformities have been documented in members of the family Ardeidae and include angular malformations, folding fractures, poorly mineralized long bones caused by trauma, nutrition deficiency, and pollutants (Feltner et al., 2006; Horgan & Duerr, 2021). This case report describes a bilateral digit fusion in an adult Eastern cattle egret and emphasizes the need to document skeletal abnormalities in avifauna for veterinary literature.

2. CASE PRESENTATION

During a bird watching survey conducted on 7th February 2026 at 10:40 hrs at Huyilalu Lake (12°18'58.6" N, 76°32'53.6" E) on the outskirts of Mysore City, Karnataka, India, an adult Eastern cattle egret (*Ardea coromanda*) was observed in flight exhibiting fused digits affecting both feet (Fig. 1). Walking, landing, and foraging behaviors could not be assessed because the bird remained airborne during the entire observation period. The lake comprises shallow marshy islets, emergent vegetation, and semi-wooded peripheral vegetation. The deformities appeared asymmetric, and both feet were seen hanging loosely during flight. Due to the absence of capture and close physical examination, detailed characterization of the lesion, including ulceration, necrosis, hyperkeratosis, or soft tissue involvement,

could not be determined. The observation was made for approximately 2 minutes.

3. DISCUSSION

Feet deformities in wild birds are multifactorial, and possible causes may include trauma, infection, developmental abnormalities, or environmental contaminants (Pourelis, 2011). Traumatic injuries, including fractures, tendon damage, fishing-line entanglement, and predation, are among the most common causes of limb deformities in water birds (Harcourt-Brown, 2002). Infections such as avian pox, pododermatitis (bumblefoot), and papillomavirus are known to affect the distal limbs and integument of birds, characterized by wart-like proliferative lesions on unfeathered regions, ranging from mild erythema to severe swelling, abscessation, and osteomyelitis, as well as benign proliferative epithelial growths involving the skin, feet, oral cavity, or cloacal region (Pass, 1989; Williams et al., 2021; Miesle, 2024). Congenital deformities in aquatic birds may result from genetic abnormalities, egg incubation anomalies, nutritional deficiencies, pollutants, or exposure to teratogenic compounds, affecting the beak, limbs, toes, vertebral column, and feathers (Pourelis, 2011). Neoplastic lesions in water birds are often associated with chronic inflammation or trauma, which may predispose tumor development on the legs and feet (Mangus et al., 2021).

Studies have reported abnormalities of the tarsometatarsus and tibiotarsus in Willet (*Tringa semipalmata*) and Eurasian Curlew (*Numenius arquata*) (Reichert et al., 2017), linear and angular toe deformities of the pelvic limbs in captive Whooping

Crane chicks (*Grus Americana*) (Kelley & Hartup, 2008); valgus deviation of the distal tibiotarsus in American Flamingo (*Phoenicopterus ruber ruber*) and Chilean Flamingo (*Phoenicopterus ruber chilensis*) (Divers et al., 1999); congenital malformation of the

hind limbs in Great Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax carbo*) affecting the pelvic appendages (Volponi, 2000) and heavy metal contamination which caused limb deformity affecting normal locomotion and posture in White Stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) (Smits et al., 2005). In

Fig. 1. Eastern cattle egret (*Ardea coromanda*) observed in flight exhibiting asymmetric bilateral feet deformities characterized by fused digits and abnormal dangling posture of the distal limbs.

Family: Ardeidae, multiple fractures and deformities of the tarsus, tibia, and metacarpal bones were reported in Grey Heron (*Ardea cinerea*) (Feltrer et al., 2006). Metabolic bone disease causing lameness, angular limb deformities, and folding fractures was reported in many Ardeid species - Western Cattle Egret (*Ardea ibis*), Great Egret (*Ardea alba*), Snowy Egret (*Egretta thula*), Black-crowned Night Heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*), Little Blue Heron (*Egretta caerulea*), and Tricolored Heron (*Egretta tricolor*) (Horgan & Duerr, 2021). Reports describing bilateral digit fusion in free-ranging Eastern cattle egrets appear to be scarce in the available literature.

Feet deformities in wading birds can impair locomotion, balance, foraging efficiency, and predator avoidance, as precise foot placement is critical for

prey capture and predator avoidance, due to reduced agility. However, some individuals survive long term by adapting their behavior, such as choosing less demanding habitats or altering foraging strategies, indicating ecological resilience (Fehlmann et al., 2021). The detection of visible morphological anomalies, behavioral deviations, and population health in free-ranging birds has important implications for wildlife health monitoring (Kelly et al., 2011). Although the limb deformity was documented in the affected individual, no diagnostic evaluation was performed to determine its precise etiology; nevertheless, such observations in colonial water birds are useful in veterinary literature and wildlife health monitoring.effects.

This report is limited by the absence of physical examination, radiographic imaging, microbiological testing, histopathological evaluation, and toxicological analysis. Therefore, the precise etiology of the deformity could not be definitively determined.

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